

Design and optimization of an electrochemical sensor for the reliable voltammetric detection of serotonin in complex biological fluids.

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Supporting information

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1. Characterization of DTDA and DTDBBF₄

Figure S1 ¹H-NMR spectrum of DTDA in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S2 ¹H-NMR spectrum of DTDBBF₄ in DMSO-d₆. The formation of the diazonium salt is followed by a shift in the chemical shift of the aromatic protons and the loss of the peak related to the amine. [1]

Figure S3 A) FT-IR spectrum of DTDBBF₄ registered in the solid phase in ATR mode. The characteristic peaks at 2264 cm⁻¹ (R-N≡N), 1552 cm⁻¹ (Aromatic C=C), 1054 cm⁻¹ (BF₄-), and 521 cm⁻¹ (S-S) are highlighted. [1] B) DSC analysis of DTDBBF₄, highlighting the stability of the diazonium salt until 100 °C, and an exothermic decomposition peak at 136 °C. [2]

2. Characterization of MWCNT-SS and MWCNT-SH

Table S1 reports the elemental composition, expressed in atomic percentage (% at), determined by XPS (**Figures S4, S5, S6, S7**).

Sample	%C	%O	%N	%S	%Fe
MWCNTs	96.80	3.20	-	-	-
MWCNT-SS	89.06	6.09	1.04	3.81	-
MWCNT-SH	89.58	5.85	2.01	2.55	-

Table S1 Elemental composition of CNTs determined by XPS.

Figure S4 High-resolution XPS spectra of A) C_{1s} and B) O_{1s} of MWCNTs; C) Survey and D) high-resolution Fe_{2p} XPS spectra of MWCNTs, highlighting the absence of Fe or other metal impurities after the purification.

Figure S5 High-Resolution XPS spectra of Sulphur 2p for A) MWCNT-SS and B) MWCNT-SH; C) TGA of MWCNTs and MWCNT-SS.

Figure S6 High-resolution XPS spectra of A) C_{1s} , B) N_{1s} and C) O_{1s} and D) Survey spectrum of MWCNT-SS.

Figure S7 High-resolution XPS spectra of A) C_{1s}, B) N_{1s}, C) O_{1s} and D) Survey spectrum of MWCNT-SH.

Figure S8. Three representative TEM micrograph of MWCNT-S-Au

Figure S9 Cyclic voltammetry of MWCNT-S-Au registered at a scan rate of 20 mV/s, showing an oxidation peak at 0.9 V which can be related to the oxidation of Au^0 to Au^+ .

3. Capacitive current of the modified electrodes

Figure S10 Cyclic voltammograms of 12 μ M serotonin solution with SPCE, MWCNT-Au/SPCE, and MWCNT-Au-MIP/SPCE. The modification of the SPCE with MWCNTs and PPy induced an increase in the capacitive current as a consequence of the high specific capacitance. [3,4]

4. Design of the Experiment (DoE)

Differential Pulse Voltammetry (DPV) was chosen as electroanalytical technique to carry out the sensing of serotonin, and a design of experiment (DoE) was used to optimize the performances of the system. Two main factors were considered: the modulation amplitude (MA), which is the intensity of each potential pulse, and modulation time (MT), which is the duration of each pulse.

A factorial design on two factors (MA and MT) and three levels was applied: for each factor three equally spaced levels (0.01 V, 0.055 V and 0.1 V for MA; 0.01 s, 0.055 s and 0.1 s for MT) were chosen (**Table S2**).

	MA (V)	MT (s)
Low	0.01	0.01
Medium	0.055	0.055
High	0.1	0.1

Table S2 Factors (MA and MT) and levels chosen for the DoE.

Subsequently, all the possible combinations (n= 9) were formulated, and each experiment was performed in triplicate with the same electrode (MWCNT-Au/SPCE). The sequence of experiments was randomized for each series.

SET 1			SET 2			SET 3		
exp n.	MA (V)	MT (s)	exp n.	MA (V)	MT (s)	exp n.	MA (V)	MT (s)
1	0	0	1	-1	0	1	-1	1
2	1	1	2	0	-1	2	0	0
3	1	-1	3	0	1	3	0	1
4	-1	0	4	1	1	4	1	0
5	0	-1	5	0	0	5	-1	0
6	-1	1	6	-1	-1	6	1	-1
7	0	1	7	1	0	7	1	1
8	1	0	8	-1	1	8	-1	-1
9	-1	-1	9	1	-1	9	0	-1

Table S3 Sets of experiments for DoE.

To evaluate the performance of the system, the following figures of merit were used:

$$FOM1 = \frac{i_F}{\Delta E_{1/2}}$$

$$FOM2 = \frac{i_F}{i_b}$$

Where i_F is the faradaic current, $\Delta E_{1/2}$ is the width of the peak at medium height and i_b is the baseline current sampled immediately before the start of the oxidation peak.

After performing the experiments, average values for FoM1 and FoM2 were determined for each factor-level combination, as reported in **Figure S9a-b**.

Figure S11 Average values of A) FoM1 and B) FoM2 from experimental data.

To obtain polynomial functions describing the dependence of FoM1 and FoM2 on MA and MT, a multiple regression analysis was performed. The following model was used to fit experimental data as a paraboloid:

$$FoM = b_0 + b_1 MA - b_2 MT - b_3 MA MT - b_4 MA^2 + b_5 MT^2 + b_6 MA^2 MT + b_7 MAMT^2 + b_8 MA^2 MT^2$$

The coefficient values for FoM1 and FoM2 are reported in **Table S4** and **Table S5**, respectively.

Regression coefficient	Corresponding term	Regression coefficient value
b_0	Intercept	-0.076
b_1	MA (V)	13.280
b_2	MT (s)	17.570
b_3	MA MT	-660.019
b_4	MA ²	-101.758
b_5	MT ²	-122.732
b_6	MA ² MT	4749.985
b_7	MAMT ²	5990.258
b_8	MA ² MT ²	-46711.216

Table S4 Coefficient values from regression for FoM1.

Regression coefficient	Corresponding term	Regression coefficient value
b_0	Intercept	-0.190
b_1	MA (V)	22.981
b_2	MT (s)	5.863
b_3	MA MT	-628.683
b_4	MA^2	-158.765
b_5	MT^2	-40.664
b_6	MA^2MT	4314.788
b_7	$MAMT^2$	4314.872
b_8	MA^2MT^2	-30199.261

Table S5 Coefficient values from regression for FoM2.

The obtained functions are represented as 3D colormap surfaces in **Figure S10a-b**, where the minimum calculated value for each function is depicted in purple and the maximum in red.

Figure S52 Derived functions for A) FoM1 and B) FoM2 from multiple regression analysis.

Since the functions offered opposite solutions, they were normalized and combined in FoM3, which is the product of the two normalized FoMs:

$$FoM3 = \frac{i_F^2}{\Delta E_{1/2} i_b}$$

The calculated values for FoM3 are represented in **Figure S11**.

Figure S63 Calculated values of FoM3.

By applying the same model equation, multiple regression yielded the coefficient values reported in Table S6.

Regression coefficient	Corresponding term	Regression coefficient value
b_0	Intercept	-0.190
b_1	MA (V)	22.981
b_2	MT (s)	5.863
b_3	MA MT	-628.683
b_4	MA ²	-158.765
b_5	MT ²	-40.664
b_6	MA ² MT	4314.788
b_7	MAMT ²	4314.872
b_8	MA ² MT ²	-30199.261

Table S6 Coefficient values from regression for FoM3.

5. Reproducibility and reusability of MWCNT-Au/SPCE

Figure S74 Experimental data for A) reusability and B) reproducibility for detection of 5-HT with MWCNT-Au/SPCE.

Figure S15. Calibration lines obtained by DPV for 5-HT with constant concentration ($5 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) of ascorbic acid (AA), Uric acid (UA), Tryptophan (Trp), and dopamine (DA)

6. Electro-polymerization of the MIP

Figure S86 Cyclic voltammograms registered during a) the MIP electro-polymerization and b) the cleaning process of the MWCNT-Au-MIP/SPCE (scan rate of 100 mV/s, PBS 0.1M KCl 0.1M)

Figure S97 SEM image of MWCNT-Au-MIP/SPCE polymerizing with 26 mM pyrrole.

Figure S108 SEM images of MWCNT-Au-MIP/SPCE using a Low Energy Detector (LED) at different magnifications.

Figure S119 SEM image of MWCNT-Au-NIP/SPCE.

Electrode	LOD	Linear range	Repeatability/ Reusability (%RSD)	Reproducibility (%RSD)	Ref.
GCE-MWCNT-Nafion/Ni(OH) ₂ NPs	15 nmol L ⁻¹ (1)	0.05 - 25 μmol L ⁻¹	2.2%	-	[5]
GCE-MWCNT-Chit	50 nmol L ⁻¹	0.05 - 16 μmol L ⁻¹	-	2.6 %	[6]
GCE-GO-MIP(Chit)	1.6 nmol L ⁻¹ (2)	0.005 - 10 μmol L ⁻¹	8.7 %	4.9 %	[7]
GCE-WO ₃ NPs	1.42 nmol L ⁻¹ (1)	0.01 - 10 μmol L ⁻¹	4.1-3.8%	3.5- 3.9%.	[8]
SPCE-FeC-AuNPs	17 nmol L ⁻¹ (2)	0.05 - 20 μmol L ⁻¹	-	4.4%	[9]
B,N-doped graphene	9-266 nmol L ⁻¹ (1)	0.10 - 224 μmol L ⁻¹	3.05%	2.08% -3.16%	[10]
TiO ₂ /AuNPs-PNB (in deep eutectic solvent)	2.47 nmol L ⁻¹ (1)	0.5 - 10 μmol L ⁻¹	3.44%	4.88%	[11]
SPCE-ZnONR-PMB	1.91 nmol L ⁻¹ (1)	0.1 - 25 μmol L ⁻¹	4.84%	5.91%	[12]
SPCE-MWCNT-AuNPs-MIP	1.7 μmol L ⁻¹ (3)	2.5 - 20 μmol L ⁻¹	4.4%	1.1%	This work

(1) It is not reported how σ is calculated.

(2) σ is calculated as the standard deviation among blank measurements.

(3) σ is calculated as the standard error on the linear regression.

Table S7 Comparison of different electrochemical sensors from literature, for detection of 5-HT, in differential pulse voltammetry

7. Study of the adsorption-dependent reaction mechanism for 5-HT oxidation

We performed a CV of 5-HT with MWCNT-Au/SPCE at different scan rates and studied the variation of the peak current to get information about the reaction mechanism. The scan rate exerts an influence on the peak current as faster scan rates usually determine higher currents. [13] The relationship between the peak current and the scan rate for electrochemically reversible electron transfer processes involving freely diffusing redox species is described by the Randles–Sevcik equation (equation S1).

$$\text{Eq. S1} \quad i_p = 0.446 nFAC^0 \left(\frac{nFvD}{RT} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Where:

- i_p (A) is the peak current;
- n is the number of electrons involved in the redox process;
- F is the Faraday constant ($=96\,485.3321\text{ s A mol}^{-1}$);
- A is the area of the electrode (cm^2);
- C^0 is the concentration of the analyte (mol cm^{-3});
- D is the diffusion coefficient of the analyte ($\text{cm}^2\text{ s}^{-1}$);
- R is the ideal gas constant ($=8,314472\text{ J K}^{-1}\text{ mol}^{-1}$);
- T (K) is the absolute temperature;
- v is the scan rate (V s^{-1}).

When the analyte is adsorbed onto the surface of the electrode, the system does not follow the Randles-Sevcik equation, but **equation S2**:

$$\text{Eq. S2} \quad i_p = \frac{n^2 F^2}{4RT} v A \Gamma^*$$

Where Γ^* (mol cm^{-2}) is the coverage factor. [13] Thus, it is possible to determine if the process is diffusion-dependent or adsorption-dependent, by registering CVs at different scan rates and subsequently plotting i_p vs v and i_p vs $v^{1/2}$ and perform a linear regression. As it is possible to appreciate in **Figure S16**, the peak current increases linearly with the scan rate ($R^2 = 0.9982$), suggesting that the ET process could be occurring via a surface-adsorbed species.

Figure S20 A) Cyclic voltammograms of 12 μM solution of serotonin at different scan rates with MWCNT-S-Au/SPCE; B) Linear dependence of peak current vs scan rate.

8. Reproducibility and repeatability of MWCNT-Au-MIP/SPCE

Figure S21 Experimental data for A) repeatability and B) reproducibility for detection of 5-HT with MWCNT-Au/SPCE.

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